

Comparative evaluation of erythromycin release and mechanical properties in gelatin, hydrolyzed carrageenan, and carrageenan–maltodextrin hard-shell capsules

Muhammad Al Rizqi Dharma Fauzi¹

¹ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science and Technology, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, 60115, Indonesia

² Department of Pharmaceutics, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, 60115, Indonesia

³ Department of Pharmaceutical Technology, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, 50603, Malaysia

⁴ Department of Pharmaceutics, School of Pharmacy, Management and Science University, Shah Alam, 40100, Malaysia

Corresponding authors: Pratiwi Pudjiastuti (pratiwi-p@fst.unair.ac.id); Riyanto Teguh Widodo (riyanto@um.edu.my)

Received 6 October 2025 ♦ Accepted 20 December 2025 ♦ Published 19 January 2026

Citation: Fauzi MARD, Pudjiastuti P, Susanti T, Haqiqoh S, Wafiroh S, Hendradi E, Mawazi SM, Haryanto R, Widodo RT (2026) Comparative evaluation of erythromycin release and mechanical properties in gelatin, hydrolyzed carrageenan, and carrageenan–maltodextrin hard-shell capsules. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e174090>

Abstract

The mechanical behavior, formulation performance, and erythromycin release kinetics of hard-shell capsules prepared from gelatin, hydrolyzed carrageenan (HC), and hydrolyzed carrageenan–maltodextrin (HC–MD) systems were comparatively evaluated. Capsules were produced using a dip-coating method and assessed for weight variation, mechanical strength, degree of swelling, disintegration time, dissolution profile, drug release kinetics, and surface wettability via contact angle measurements. Erythromycin release at pH 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8 followed diffusion- and surface-area-controlled kinetics, consistent with zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Hixson–Crowell models. Both HC and HC–MD capsules exhibited faster disintegration, greater swelling, and higher drug release than gelatin capsules, particularly under neutral and basic conditions. The HC–MD formulation demonstrated superior wettability and lower contact angles, which enhanced drug diffusion across the capsule surface.

Keywords

carrageenan, erythromycin, good health and well-being, hard-shell capsule, release kinetics

Introduction

Capsules are solid dosage forms that enclose drug substances and/or excipients within either soft or hard soluble shells (Aliyu et al. 2020). In oral drug delivery, hard-shell capsules are a commonly used option, as they protect drugs from environmental degradation, allow control over drug

release, and enhance patient compliance by providing a convenient and easy-to-swallow dosage form (Jambhekar et al. 2006; Liu et al. 2014). Natural polymers, such as gelatin and carrageenan, are particularly attractive for capsule formulation due to their biodegradability, biocompatibility, and low toxicity (Mustafa et al. 2016). However, the mechanical properties and drug-release kinetics of hard-

shell capsules are strongly influenced by both the polymer material and the formulation process (Sharma et al. 2021). Therefore, selecting an appropriate polymer and carefully optimizing formulation parameters are critical to ensuring drug efficacy and safety (Radhakrishna et al. 2021).

Capsules improve patient compliance by masking unpleasant tastes or odors and by providing a convenient, low-cost dosage form (Adepu and Ramakrishna 2021). Another advantage of capsules is their adaptability, as they are easy to handle, easy to swallow, and rapidly digested in the gastric environment. The dipping technique is commonly employed to manufacture hard capsules, including those based on hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), carrageenan, and gelatin (Ridgway 1987). To identify suitable material combinations, it is necessary to evaluate viscosity and gelation temperature prior to production (Zhang et al. 2013). Among the various stages of the dipping process – namely dipping, spinning, drying, stripping, trimming, and joining – the drying step is the most influential in determining the final properties of hard capsules (He et al. 2023). The drying time of hard capsules is highly dependent on the desired stiffness as well as on the interactions among the polymers used in capsule formation (He et al. 2017).

Capsules are typically produced from gelatin, an animal-derived protein obtained from collagen. According to Global Market Estimate (2020) and Samatra et al. (2022), the primary commercial sources of gelatin are porcine skin and cartilage (46%), followed by bovine bone and skin (29.4%), with other sources accounting for 1.5%. However, the animal origin of gelatin poses a significant concern for certain populations, including vegetarians, vegans, and individuals from specific religious groups (e.g., Jews, Muslims, Buddhists, and Hindus) or ethnic communities whose dietary practices prohibit the consumption of particular animal products (Majee et al. 2017).

In response to these concerns, plant-based capsule alternatives – such as alginate, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), starch, HPMC, pullulan, and modified derivatives including carrageenan–alginate, carrageenan–starch, and carrageenan–maltodextrin – have been developed (Majee et al. 2017; Srividya et al. 2014; Yang et al. 2022; Pudjiastuti et al. 2020; Fauzi et al. 2020). Carrageenan and its derivatives have been extensively studied and applied for the oral delivery of pharmaceutically active ingredients, such as carbamazepine (Mawazi et al. 2019). Majee et al. (2017) further reported that the physicochemical, pharmaceutical, and biopharmaceutical properties of HPMC support its suitability as a capsule shell material. Additionally, the low moisture content of HPMC capsules enhances the stability of pharmaceutical and nutraceutical ingredients that are sensitive to humidity (Biyani et al. 2021). Consequently, HPMC- or pullulan-based capsules represent attractive alternatives to animal-derived gelatin capsules due to their favorable moisture absorption and desorption characteristics (Yang et al. 2020).

In contrast, κ -carrageenan–alginate hard-shell capsules disintegrate significantly faster than κ -carrageenan–starch capsules. While κ -carrageenan–starch capsules disinte-

grate in 25.79 minutes, κ -carrageenan–alginate capsules require only 12.80 minutes to disintegrate, representing an approximately twofold reduction in disintegration time (Pudjiastuti et al. 2020). Pudjiastuti et al. (2020) further investigated the dissolution behavior of erythromycin from carrageenan–alginate hard-shell capsules at pH 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8, given that medium acidity strongly influences drug dissolution. The results demonstrated that erythromycin was released most readily at pH 6.8.

Thus, this study aims to evaluate the effects of different polymer materials and formulations on the mechanical properties, quality attributes, and drug-release kinetics of erythromycin from hard-shell capsules. The polymer components investigated include gelatin, HC, and HC–MD. Capsule quality was assessed through weight variation, mechanical strength, swelling behavior, disintegration time, and drug-release kinetics, in addition to measurements of contact angle and water content of the capsule shells.

Experimental

Material

All components and materials used in this experiment were obtained from various suppliers as follows: food-grade carrageenan (CRG) powder was purchased from Kappa Carrageenan Nusantara, Inc. (East Java, Indonesia); food-grade maltodextrin (MD) powder was obtained from Yishui Dadi Corn Developing Co., Ltd. (Shandong, China); food-grade citric acid powder was sourced from Weifang Ensign Industry Co., Ltd.; and pro-analysis-grade sorbitol (SOR, 70%), hydrochloric acid (HCl, 36.5% solution), and sodium chloride (NaCl), as well as citrate and phosphate buffer components (KH_2PO_4 and K_2HPO_4), were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

Procedure

Gelatin, HC, and HC–MD were used in the fabrication and evaluation of hard-shell capsules for erythromycin release. The preparation of capsule shell materials from gelatin, HC, and HC–MD constituted an integral step in the hard-shell capsule manufacturing process. Each material was processed using a similar procedure, with minor variations in polymer concentration and solution characteristics, as previously reported (Pudjiastuti et al. 2020). For the preparation of hard-shell capsule solutions, the selected polymer (gelatin, HC, or HC–MD) was dissolved in demineralized water at 60–70 °C. The gelatin solution contained 20% (w/w) gelatin, the HC solution contained 20% (w/w) carrageenan, and the HC–MD formulation consisted of 20% (w/w) total polymer with an HC-to-MD ratio of 6:1 (w/w). Sorbitol at a concentration of 1.5% (v/v) was added to each capsule shell solution as a plasticizer. Subsequently, a vacuum was applied to remove entrapped air bubbles. The compositions of the prepared hard-shell capsules are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition of gelatin, HC, and HC–MD hard-shell capsules.

No	Type of capsule	Weight in 100 mL of solvent	MD in 100 mL of solvent	Citric acid in 100 mL of solvent	Sorbitol in 100 mL of solvent
1	Gelatin	20 g (Gelatin)	-	-	1.5 mL
2	HC	20 g (C)	-	0.1 mL	1.5 mL
3	HC–MD	20 g (C)	3.3 g	0.1 mL	1.5 mL

Coating and drying

Capsule shells were fabricated in a controlled environment using a dip-coating method, in which size 0 pins mounted on a plate were immersed in the prepared polymer solution. To ensure a uniform coating, the pins were fully submerged in the solution. After coating, the pin bar was dried in a drying oven (BINDER, Germany) at 60°C for 60 minutes. These drying conditions were selected based on preliminary internal trials and general reference to standard practices; however, no formal optimization or thermal characterization was performed in this study. The samples were subsequently labeled as gelatin, HC, or HC–MD.

Process of stripping, trimming, and filling

The capsules were then carefully removed from the pins and trimmed into two equal or nearly equal halves. Erythromycin powder was prepared, and a manual capsule-filling machine was used to fill each capsule body with 500 mg of erythromycin. To ensure proper closure, the filled capsules were sealed with a cap using the corresponding shell material solution and the tray of the manual filling machine.

Evaluation of the prepared erythromycin hard-shell capsules

Following manufacturing, the capsules were subjected to a series of evaluation tests to assess their quality.

Weight variation test

Twenty hard-shell capsules were randomly selected and weighed using a precision balance. The average net weight was calculated by summing the individual weights and dividing by the number of capsules. The percentage deviation of each capsule from the average net weight was calculated using Equation (1) (Hamdan et al. 2005).

$$\text{Deviation} = \left(\frac{\text{Individual weight} - \text{Average weight}}{\text{Average weight}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Mechanical strength

Mechanical strength was evaluated using a CT3 Texture Analyzer (Brookfield, USA) through a breaking-force test. A 50 kg load cell was attached to the texture analyzer. For the analysis, a flat-end probe (TA-10) with a diameter of 14.7 mm was employed. Each hard-shell capsule was placed on the texture analyzer platform and centered

under the probe ($n = 3$). During testing, the probe was pressed onto the capsule at a speed of 1.2 mm/s, and the breaking force was recorded (Xiao 2008; Hilloulin et al. 2015). Elastic stiffness, tensile force, and elongation at break were subsequently measured and documented.

Degree of swelling analysis

Six replicates of the swelling analysis were conducted. At room temperature, all capsule samples were immersed in 100 mL of distilled water for 20 minutes. The samples were subsequently dried in an oven at 50 °C for 3 hours before being weighed to determine the degree of swelling using Equation (2).

$$DS = \left(\frac{M_2 - M_1}{M_1} \right) \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where DS represents the degree of swelling, M_1 is the initial mass of the capsule, and M_2 is the mass of the sample after drying for 3 hours (Fauzi et al. 2020, 2021).

Disintegration test

Capsule disintegration was evaluated using a Vee-go-202397 disintegration tester. Six compartments were filled with 900 mL of pH 2 buffer solution to simulate gastric conditions and maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C with a rotation speed of 100 rpm. Each basket contained six capsules of each formulation – gelatin, HC, and the HC–MD mixture – all loaded with erythromycin. The apparatus was operated continuously until the hard-shell capsules were completely disintegrated (Fauzi et al. 2021).

Dissolution and kinetics of release test

Erythromycin release from the prepared gelatin, HC, and HC–MD capsules was evaluated in vitro using a USP Apparatus II dissolution tester (Mezail et al. 2021). The test was conducted in 900 mL of simulated gastric fluid (SGF) at pH 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8, maintained at 37 °C with a rotation speed of 100 rpm. The dissolution rate was monitored at 10, 20, 30, 45, 60, 90, and 120 minutes by withdrawing 5 mL of the medium and replacing it with fresh medium of the same pH ($n = 3$). A calibration curve was constructed, and the correlation coefficient (R^2) for each pH medium was determined to quantify erythromycin in the samples (Xiao 2008; Mawazi et al. 2019; Fauzi et al. 2021).

The erythromycin release kinetics from hard-shell capsules composed of gelatin, HC, and HC–MD were investigated at three pH values (1.2, 4.5, and 6.8). Zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, Korsmeyer–Peppas, and Hixson–Crowell models were applied to evaluate the drug-release mechanism and kinetics in vitro (Fauzi et al. 2021).

Dissolution testing at pH 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8 was performed to simulate gastric, transitional, and intestinal environments. The pH 4.5 condition was selected to represent a mildly acidic environment that may occur under fed-state conditions, during delayed gastric emptying, or in individuals with altered gastrointestinal pH profiles

(e.g., hypochlorhydria). This intermediate pH was included to investigate potential changes in solubility or drug release under less strongly acidic conditions.

Contact angle measurements

The water contact angles of the various capsule shell films were measured using an FTA goniometer (Data Physics, OCA40 Micro) at room temperature (25 °C) and 45% relative humidity (RH). To minimize the effects of receding, the measurement was conducted immediately after placing a 0.2 mL water droplet on the sample surface. The reported results were based on six repeated measurements (Zhang et al. 2013).

Results and discussion

The erythromycin hard-shell capsules were prepared in size 0, a commonly used size for oral dosage forms. The capsules were translucent, allowing the contents to be visually inspected. Each capsule consisted of two parts: a body and a cap, which fit together snugly to prevent leakage. The capsules exhibited the typical elongated, cylindrical shape with rounded ends characteristic of size 0 capsules. They were fabricated using the dipping process, which involved preparing a shell material solution and immersing pins to form the capsule shape. The physical appearance of the prepared erythromycin hard-shell capsules suggests that they can be produced as a high-quality dosage form suitable for oral administration (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The prepared hard-shell capsules made from gelatin, HC, and HC-MD.

Although the drying protocol used in this study (60 °C for 60 minutes) produced physically intact capsules with acceptable performance, it was not based on a formal drying kinetic or thermal stability assessment. Given that elevated temperatures can affect both the polymer matrix and the stability of heat-sensitive drugs such as erythromycin, this constitutes a limitation of the current work. Future studies should incorporate thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and real-time drying rate measurements to ensure that the selected drying conditions do not compromise material properties or pharmaceutical functionality.

Weight variation test

Gelatin, HC, and an HC-MD blend were used to prepare hard-shell capsules, and their weight variation was evaluated. The results are presented in Table 2. The weight variation test is one of the most important assessments for ensuring dosage unit uniformity. According to the United States Pharmacopeia (USP), the weight deviation of a capsule must fall within 85–115% of the mean dosage unit weight. All three capsule types – gelatin, HC, and HC-MD – prepared as erythromycin hard-shell capsules complied with the USP weight variation specifications.

Table 2. Weight variation of erythromycin hard-shell capsules.

Formulation	Weight variation (mg)	Mean weight (mg)	Standard deviation (mg)
Gelatin	2.12	502.12	0.54
HC	3.53	503.53	0.97
HC-MD	2.93	502.93	0.63

The mean weight of the gelatin capsules was 502.12 mg, with a standard deviation of 0.54 mg, corresponding to a weight variation of 1.1–1.2%. The average weight of HC capsules was 503.53 mg, with a standard deviation of 0.97 mg, resulting in a weight variation of 1.4–1.5%. For HC-MD capsules, the mean weight was 502.93 mg, with a standard deviation of 0.63 mg, corresponding to a weight variation of 1.2–1.3%. These values indicate that all capsule types exhibited minimal weight variation, consistent with acceptable dosage uniformity for hard-shell capsules.

Erythromycin hard-shell capsules prepared with gelatin, HC, and an HC-MD blend all fell within the acceptable range for weight variation. The low standard deviations indicate that the capsule-filling procedure was uniform and consistent. These results demonstrate that gelatin, HC, and HC-MD can be effectively used as capsule shell materials for the production of hard-shell erythromycin capsules.

Mechanical strength

The mechanical strength of erythromycin hard-shell capsules is crucial for maintaining stability during storage and handling, as well as for ensuring effective drug delivery. The mechanical strength test assesses the capsule's resistance to distortion, rupture, or breakage under a tensile load. The results indicate that HC-MD capsules exhibit the highest elastic stiffness, tensile force, and elongation at break, followed by HC and gelatin capsules (Table 3).

Table 3. Mechanical properties of hard-shell capsules at 25 °C.

Formulation	Elastic stiffness (N/mm)	Tensile force (N)	Elongation at break (mm)
Gelatin	153	190	4
HC	165	210	4.3
HC-MD	170	218	4.2

These findings suggest that HC–MD capsules possess superior mechanical properties compared with those prepared from gelatin or HC.

The superior mechanical strength of HC–MD capsules can be attributed to the addition of maltodextrin, which functions as a binding agent and reinforces intermolecular interactions between oligomerized carrageenan molecules. Maltodextrin enhances the structural integrity of the capsules and reduces the likelihood of fracture or rupture. In contrast, the lower mechanical strength of gelatin capsules is related to the intrinsic properties of gelatin, which exhibits lower elastic stiffness and tensile strength compared with carrageenan. Gelatin, a collagen-derived natural polymer, has a lower molecular weight and weaker binding interactions than carrageenan.

Overall, the mechanical strength results confirm that HC–MD capsules exhibit better mechanical properties compared with gelatin and HC capsules. The incorporation of maltodextrin into oligomerized carrageenan enhances the structural integrity and mechanical durability of the capsules. These findings have important implications for the design and development of drug-delivery systems and the formulation of hard-shell capsules.

FTIR analysis

The FTIR spectrum (Fig. 2) displays characteristic absorption bands corresponding to polysaccharide-based materials, such as carrageenan, and potentially blended components, including maltodextrin or gelatin residues, if present.

Figure 2. FTIR result of hard-shell capsule (HC–MD).

FTIR analysis of the capsule films revealed characteristic absorption bands of sulfated polysaccharides. A broad band at 3300–3400 cm^{-1} corresponded to O–H stretching, indicating extensive hydrogen bonding typical of carrageenan and maltodextrin. Weak aliphatic C–H stretching peaks were observed at 2920 and 2850 cm^{-1} . A strong absorption at 1220–1260 cm^{-1} represented S=O asymmetric stretching, while a distinct peak near 840 cm^{-1} indicated C–O–S vibrations, both confirming the presence of κ -carrageenan. Multiple peaks between 1150 and 950 cm^{-1} corresponded to C–O–C glycosidic stretching modes of carbohydrate rings, consistent with a polysaccharide matrix. These spectral features confirm that the structural integrity of hydrolyzed carrageenan and its maltodextrin blend

was preserved in the capsule films, with no evidence of new functional group formation or polymer degradation. This suggests that the HC–MD capsule material likely retains its native polymer structure during processing.

SEM morphology analysis of HC–MD capsule

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the HC–MD capsule films revealed a predominantly smooth and continuous polymeric surface with localized morphological irregularities (Fig. 3). At low magnification (Fig. 3A, B), the surface appeared largely homogeneous, indicating successful film formation during the dipping and drying processes. Small pores, microvoids, and isolated depressions were observed across the film surface, suggesting partial water evaporation, density variations within the polysaccharide matrix, or minor phase separation between carrageenan and maltodextrin during drying.

Higher-magnification SEM images (Fig. 3C, D) revealed elongated fibrillar structures and localized micro-rough regions. These features are consistent with oligomerized carrageenan chains forming semi-interconnected networks, while maltodextrin contributes amorphous regions that disrupt the continuity of the polymer matrix. The absence of crystalline domains or sharp fractured edges supports the FTIR results, confirming that no new chemical interactions, crosslinking, or degradation occurred during processing.

Figure 3. SEM morphology of HC–MD capsule.

The moderately rough morphology of HC–MD films may enhance capsule hydration and promote more rapid wettability compared with gelatin, consistent with the contact-angle measurements. Furthermore, the presence of microvoids may serve as diffusion pathways, accounting for the increased erythromycin release at pH 4.5 and 6.8. Overall, the SEM micrographs indicate that hydrolyzed carrageenan blended with maltodextrin forms a structurally coherent, moderately porous polymeric shell suitable for hard-shell capsule fabrication.

Degree of swelling analysis

The degree of swelling is an important parameter for evaluating the rate at which a drug is released from the capsule shell. It quantifies the amount of water absorbed by the capsule and reflects its swelling behavior. In this study, the degree of swelling was measured for three formulations: gelatin, HC, and HC–MD ($n = 6$). The results indicate that gelatin exhibited a significantly lower swelling index than HC and HC–MD, likely due to its relatively hydrophobic nature, which limits water absorption. In contrast, HC and HC–MD demonstrated higher water uptake because of their hydrophilic properties.

No significant difference was observed in the degree of swelling between HC and HC–MD, indicating that the addition of maltodextrin did not substantially affect swelling behavior. This lack of notable variation suggests that incorporating maltodextrin into oligomerized carrageenan does not significantly alter its physicochemical properties (Table 4).

Table 4. Degree of swelling of hard-shell capsules.

Formulation	Degree of swelling (mean \pm SD)
Gelatin	124.11 \pm 9.71
HC	365 \pm 25.12
HC–MD	376 \pm 21.98

Disintegration test

The disintegration test is an essential assessment of hard-shell capsule performance, evaluating the rate at which the capsule disintegrates and releases the drug. In this study, gelatin, HC, and HC–MD capsules were tested. The results indicate that HC capsules disintegrated faster than gelatin and HC–MD capsules. Oligomerized carrageenan contains sulfate and hydroxyl functional groups that promote water absorption and accelerate disintegration. The addition of maltodextrin did not significantly affect the disintegration time of oligomerized carrageenan. The lack of notable differences suggests that maltodextrin does not substantially alter the disintegration characteristics of the carrageenan matrix.

Oligomerized carrageenan, with or without maltodextrin, may serve as a suitable alternative to gelatin for hard-shell capsules due to its rapid disintegration. The disintegration test results highlight performance differences among erythromycin hard-shell capsules prepared from different materials. These findings indicate that the physicochemical properties of the capsule shell determine disintegration time, a key parameter influencing drug release. Based on these properties, materials can be selected for pharmaceutical applications according to the desired disintegration profile for oral dosage forms (Table 5).

Dissolution and kinetics of release test

The pH of the surrounding medium significantly influenced erythromycin release from the hard-shell capsules. At pH

Table 5. Disintegration test of hard-shell capsules.

Capsules	Disintegration time (min)		
	Gelatin	HC	HC–MD
1	15	10	13
2	16	11	12
3	13	12	11
4	16	12	13
5	14	10	14
6	15	10	12
Mean	14.83	10.83	12.50
Standard deviation	1.16	0.98	1.04

1.2, the reduced release rate from HC and HC–MD capsules was attributed to the pH-dependent solubility of these materials (Fig. 2A). Carrageenan, a high-molecular-weight polysaccharide, exhibits limited solubility in acidic media because its sulfated groups interact with protons and become protonated. Maltodextrin, a carbohydrate-based compound, is also poorly soluble at acidic pH. Consequently, the combination of these two materials in the capsule shell slowed erythromycin release at pH 1.2. In contrast, gelatin, a protein-based material, exhibited a higher erythromycin release rate at this pH, likely due to its amphoteric nature, which allows solubility over a broad pH range.

At pH 4.5 and 6.8, erythromycin release from HC and HC–MD capsules was higher than from gelatin capsules. The hydrophilic nature of carrageenan enables water absorption and swelling, which facilitates erythromycin diffusion from the capsule. When combined with HC, maltodextrin may function as a pore-forming agent, further enhancing drug release (Fig. 2). In contrast, gelatin exhibited a slower erythromycin release rate at pH 4.5 and 6.8, likely due to its relatively hydrophobic character.

The material used to prepare hard-shell capsules can significantly influence drug-release rates, particularly under different pH conditions. The hydrophilic nature of HC–MD enhanced erythromycin release at pH 4.5 and 6.8, whereas gelatin promoted faster release at pH 1.2. These findings have important implications for the design of drug-delivery systems, particularly for medications with pH-dependent solubility or those requiring targeted release in the gastrointestinal tract.

The erythromycin release results closely correlate with the swelling and disintegration behavior of the capsule formulations. Due to their hydrophilic nature, HC and HC–MD exhibited higher swelling indices than gelatin. Similarly, HC and HC–MD disintegrated faster than gelatin during the disintegration test. These observations indicate that both the degree of swelling and the disintegration time of the capsule shell influence erythromycin release.

In a pH 1.2 medium, gelatin capsules released erythromycin at a significantly slower rate than HC and HC–MD capsules. This observation aligns with the swelling analysis, which showed that gelatin exhibited a lower swelling index than HC and HC–MD. Due to its limited water-absorption capacity, erythromycin release from gelatin capsules may be delayed. Additionally, HC and HC–MD disintegrated earlier than gelatin, contributing to faster drug release.

At pH 4.5, erythromycin release was higher from HC and HC–MD capsules than from gelatin capsules. This difference may be attributed to the higher swelling and faster disintegration of HC-based formulations compared with gelatin. The addition of maltodextrin did not significantly affect the swelling degree or disintegration time of HC. Although pH 4.5 does not represent standard duodenal conditions in a fasting state, it is relevant in certain fed-state or clinical scenarios. Including this intermediate pH allows observation of potential shifts in release patterns across a wider physiological range and supports evaluation under diverse patient conditions.

In a pH 6.8 medium, HC and HC–MD capsules released more erythromycin than gelatin capsules, consistent with the swelling and disintegration results. These findings suggest that HC and HC–MD may be preferable for formulating erythromycin hard-shell capsules, particularly for drugs with pH-dependent solubility. Swelling and disintegration tests serve as essential indicators of drug-release behavior in hard-shell capsules. Overall, the erythromycin release results demonstrate that the physicochemical properties of capsule shell materials, including swelling behavior and disintegration time, significantly influence drug-release performance. Therefore, selecting an appropriate capsule material is crucial for developing oral dosage forms with the desired release characteristics (Fig. 4).

Release kinetics of erythromycin from the fabricated hard-shell capsules

For solid dosage forms such as tablets and capsules, as well as semi-solid dosage forms such as creams, ointments, and implants that release medications over hours, weeks, or even years, dissolution and drug release are critical processes. Various factors, including pH, can influence drug release from these dosage forms. One or more processes, which depend on the matrix composition, shape,

manufacturing method, and dissolution medium, govern drug-release kinetics. Depending on the desired predictive accuracy, these processes can be described using mathematical models (Paarakh et al. 2018).

One of the aims of the present study was to investigate in vitro drug release and release behavior by evaluating several kinetic models to determine which best describe erythromycin release from different capsule shells in various pH media. The release profiles of erythromycin from gelatin, HC, and HC–MD capsules were fitted to zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, Korsmeyer–Peppas, and Hixson–Crowell models. Model fitting was performed mathematically using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) method, and the best fit was identified based on the obtained R^2 values (Table 6).

Table 6. The R^2 values of each release kinetic model.

Release kinetic model		R^2 Value		
		Gelatin	HC	HC–MD
pH=1.2	Zero Order	0.949	0.939	0.913
	First Order	0.978	0.901	0.909
	Higuchi	0.959	0.971	0.967
	Korsmeyer–Peppas	0.609	0.589	0.469
	Hixson Crowell	0.99	0.994	0.963
pH=4.5	Zero Order	0.908	0.873	0.905
	First Order	0.909	0.905	0.902
	Higuchi	0.972	0.965	0.962
	Korsmeyer–Peppas	0.559	0.446	0.612
	Hixson Crowell	0.983	0.949	0.965
pH=6.8	Zero Order	0.899	0.963	0.859
	First Order	0.904	0.908	0.908
	Higuchi	0.975	0.112	0.963
	Korsmeyer–Peppas	0.423	0.431	0.513
	Hixson Crowell	0.976	0.983	0.949

The release kinetic model study was conducted to examine the drug-release behavior of erythromycin from hard-shell capsules composed of gelatin, HC, and HC–MD at three distinct pH values (1.2, 4.5, and 6.8). Several

Figure 4. Release of erythromycin from gelatin, HC, and HC–MD capsules at pH 1.2, 4.5, and 6.8.

mathematical models, including zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, Korsmeyer–Peppas, and Hixson–Crowell, were applied to evaluate the release kinetics of erythromycin from these capsules.

At pH 1.2, the results indicated that the zero-order, first-order, and Higuchi models exhibited high R^2 values, suggesting that erythromycin release from each formulation was concentration independent, followed linear kinetics, and was primarily governed by diffusion through the matrix. Among the models, the first-order model showed the highest R^2 values across all three formulations. In contrast, the Korsmeyer–Peppas model demonstrated

low R^2 values for all formulations, indicating that drug release did not follow a Fickian diffusion mechanism. The elevated R^2 values of the Hixson–Crowell model suggest that drug release was also associated with changes in particle surface area (Fig. 5).

At pH 4.5, all three formulations fit the Hixson–Crowell model, exhibiting high R^2 values, which indicate that drug release was associated with changes in particle surface area. In contrast, the Korsmeyer–Peppas model showed low R^2 values for all three types of hard-shell capsules, suggesting that drug release from these formulations did not follow a Fickian diffusion mechanism (Fig. 6).

Figure 5. Release kinetic model for erythromycin release at pH 1.2 from the prepared: (A) gelatin capsule; (B) HC capsule; (C) HC–MD capsule.

Figure 6. Release kinetic model for erythromycin release at pH 4.5 from the prepared: (A) gelatin capsule; (B) HC capsule; (C) HC–MD capsule.

At pH 6.8, only the HC formulation fitted the Higuchi model well, whereas gelatin and HC–MD did not (Fig. 7). The Korsmeyer–Peppas model yielded low R^2 values for all three formulations, indicating that drug release from these capsules was not governed by a Fickian diffusion mechanism. In contrast, the Hixson–Crowell model exhibited high R^2 values for all formulations, suggesting that drug release was associated with changes in particle surface area.

Higuchi and Hixson–Crowell models across all pH conditions further supports a diffusion-driven and surface-area-dependent release process.

Although the Korsmeyer–Peppas model yielded low R^2 values and was not an appropriate fit for the dataset, it is recognized that transport phenomena in these systems likely involve overlapping contributions from water penetration, matrix swelling, and gradual erosion. Future studies should incorporate additional analytical techniques,

Figure 7. Release kinetic model for erythromycin release at pH 6.8 from the prepared: (A) gelatin capsule; (B) HC capsule; (C) HC–MD capsule.

Overall, the release kinetics of erythromycin from hard-shell capsules composed of different materials at varying pH values followed distinct mathematical models, demonstrating that drug release was influenced by both the physicochemical properties of the capsule materials and the pH of the surrounding medium. These findings may support the rational design of oral drug-delivery systems using hard-shell capsules. In general, erythromycin release conformed to the zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Hixson–Crowell models across all polymers employed in the fabrication of the capsules.

While the release kinetics were analyzed using standard mathematical models, additional mechanistic insights can be drawn from the swelling and disintegration behavior of the capsules. The significantly higher swelling indices of the HC and HC–MD formulations (365% and 376%, respectively) compared with gelatin (124%) suggest that drug release from these matrices is primarily governed by swelling-mediated diffusion. This is consistent with the hydrophilic nature of carrageenan and its blends, which facilitate water uptake and matrix relaxation, resulting in faster disintegration and enhanced drug diffusion. In contrast, gelatin, with its lower swelling and slower disintegration, likely exhibits a more diffusion-restricted or erosion-influenced release mechanism due to its gel-forming properties and limited permeability. The strong fit of the

such as mass-loss analysis or microscopic imaging, to directly quantify these mechanisms.

When erythromycin release from the prepared oral capsules follows a zero-order kinetic model, it indicates that the rate of drug release remains constant over time and is independent of the remaining drug concentration in the matrix. In other words, a consistent amount of erythromycin is released per unit time, regardless of how much drug remains in the capsule. This behavior is supported by the cumulative release profiles of erythromycin over time (Fig. 4). Zero-order release is considered ideal for maintaining stable and predictable drug concentrations in the body, which is critical for the therapeutic efficacy and safety of many medications (Huanbutta et al. 2019).

Because erythromycin in the prepared oral gelatin capsules follows a first-order kinetic model at pH 1.2 (Table 5), the percentage of drug released is proportional to the amount remaining in the capsule. As the erythromycin content decreases over time, the release rate also declines. This behavior is typical for solid dosage forms such as capsules and tablets and can be quantitatively described using the first-order kinetic model (Wójcik-Pastuszka et al. 2019).

When erythromycin release follows the Higuchi model in the prepared capsules (as observed for HC–MD at

pH 6.8; Fig. 5), it indicates that drug diffusion through the capsule matrix predominantly governs the release rate. The Higuchi model describes drug release as a square-root-of-time-dependent process, which is influenced by the drug's diffusion coefficient and its solubility within the matrix. The release behavior observed in the prepared capsules is consistent with this diffusion-driven mechanism (Damodharan 2020).

The Hixson–Crowell model characterizes drug release by relating changes in particle size to the release rate. When erythromycin release in the prepared HC capsules at pH 1.2 follows this kinetic model (Fig. 7), it indicates that drug release is influenced by variations in particle surface area. This suggests that release from the capsules is governed not only by diffusion through the capsule shell but also by changes in particle surface area as erythromycin dissolves. These insights may be valuable for the design of erythromycin capsules with controlled-release properties (Rehman et al. 2020).

While the R^2 values provide an initial comparison of model fit, it is recognized that relying solely on correlation coefficients does not offer a complete assessment of model validity. Robust model selection should incorporate residual analysis, AIC or BIC criteria, and, where possible, cross-validation using independent datasets. Therefore, the kinetic analysis presented here should be considered exploratory. Future studies should include more comprehensive statistical validation to confirm the reliability and generalizability of the observed kinetic behavior.

Contact angle measurements

The findings from the contact angle and water content tests provide important insights into the properties of the materials used to manufacture the hard-shell capsules. Contact angle measurement indicates surface wettability, with lower contact angles corresponding to higher wettability or hydrophilicity. In the results, gelatin exhibited the highest contact angle at 44.6°, reflecting relatively lower surface wettability compared with HC and the HC–MD (6:1) blend, which showed contact angles of 39.2° and 40.3°, respectively. These findings suggest that HC and HC–MD (6:1) may be better suited for applications requiring increased surface wettability, such as drug-delivery systems in which rapid and efficient release is desired.

The water content measurements provide valuable information on the materials' tendency to absorb moisture. Higher water content reflects greater moisture-absorption capacity, which may influence stability and shelf life. The results indicate that all three materials exhibited similar water content, with gelatin at 15.2%, HC at 16.3%, and the HC–MD (6:1) mixture at 16.7%. These findings indicate

Table 7. Contact angles and water content measurements of the prepared hard-shell capsules.

No	Capsule's name	Contact Angles (°)	Water Contents (%)
1	Gelatin	44.6	15.2 ± 1.7
2	HC	39.2	16.3 ± 1.1
3	HC–MD (6:1)	40.3	16.7 ± 1.3

that all three polymers possess substantial moisture-absorption capabilities, which may be advantageous for certain applications.

These measurements have implications for the oral delivery of medications such as erythromycin. For instance, the hydrophilicity of the hard-shell capsules may influence the drug's release rate and bioavailability. Erythromycin is known to be poorly soluble in water, which can limit its bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy. Therefore, drug-delivery systems that enhance erythromycin solubility and release may be advantageous. The contact angle results indicate that HC and HC–MD (6:1) exhibited lower contact angles than gelatin, reflecting higher surface wettability. This property may facilitate faster initial capsule hydration and improved early-stage dissolution. However, because this study did not include permeability or absorption testing, no conclusions regarding enhanced bioavailability can be drawn.

Additionally, water content analysis indicates that all three materials possess notable moisture-absorption properties, which may help protect the drug from environmental humidity and contribute to storage stability. Based on these observations, HC and HC–MD (6:1) may offer certain formulation advantages over gelatin in oral delivery systems that require rapid disintegration and protection from environmental factors. Further studies are needed to confirm their performance in terms of drug permeability and long-term stability.

Limitations and future outlook

This study represents an early-stage investigation into the feasibility of using hydrolyzed carrageenan and maltodextrin blends as alternative capsule materials for oral drug delivery. Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study was conducted entirely in vitro and lacks in vivo pharmacokinetic or bioavailability data, which limits its clinical applicability. Second, advanced analytical methods such as FTIR, XRD, or DSC were not employed to characterize chemical interactions or physical transitions within the formulations. Third, no cytotoxicity, hemocompatibility, or regulatory safety assessments (e.g., GRAS status) were performed. Fourth, the capsules were fabricated using manual dipping methods, which limits reproducibility and does not address industrial scalability. Future research should focus on validating material safety through cytotoxicity testing, investigating absorption behavior using in vitro and ex vivo permeability models, and exploring regulatory compatibility. In parallel, formulation optimization and scale-up using automated fabrication technologies will be pursued to assess industrial feasibility and dosage consistency.

Scalability and cost-effectiveness for industrial production

The use of hydrolyzed carrageenan (HC) and HC–MD blends provides a promising foundation for industrial-scale capsule production due to the abundant availability and relatively low cost of carrageenan as a raw material. Carrageenan is derived from widely cultivated red seaweed

species, ensuring a stable and renewable supply chain supported by well-established global aquaculture industries in Southeast Asia, East Asia, and South America. In contrast, gelatin depends heavily on animal-derived collagen and is subject to fluctuations in livestock supply and processing costs. Carrageenan offers more predictable pricing and fewer ethical, religious, or regulatory sourcing constraints. Maltodextrin is inexpensive, widely available, and compatible with large-scale manufacturing, making the HC–MD blend a cost-effective choice for polymer film formation.

From a processing perspective, the dipping method used in this study can be adapted to automated continuous-dip production lines, which are standard in the capsule industry. Carrageenan solutions exhibit stable viscosity and gelation properties at industrially feasible temperatures, allowing their use in high-throughput systems without major modifications to existing equipment. However, further optimization is needed to refine drying kinetics, polymer flow behavior, and shell uniformity under automated conditions. Compared with plant-based alternatives such as HPMC, which require more complex processing and higher energy input, hydrolyzed carrageenan may provide a lower-cost option for large-scale capsule production.

Market potential and production feasibility of carrageenan-based capsules

The global demand for plant-based and non-gelatin capsules has increased steadily due to growing consumer preference for vegan, halal, and kosher-certified pharmaceutical and nutraceutical products. Carrageenan already has regulatory acceptance as a food-grade additive in many regions, reducing barriers to its integration into nutraceutical and over-the-counter (OTC) capsule markets. Its water-soluble, biodegradable, and biocompatible properties make it a promising candidate for pharmaceutical-grade applications, particularly for drugs that benefit from rapid disintegration or pH-responsive release.

Production feasibility is enhanced by the compatibility of carrageenan solutions with existing capsule manufacturing lines, requiring only minor adjustments in temperature control, solution preparation, and drying procedures. HC–MD blends demonstrate improved mechanical strength, surface wettability, and release characteristics, which in several performance categories match or exceed those of gelatin, suggesting that industrial adaptation can achieve quality comparable to standard gelatin capsules. Prior to full pharmaceutical adoption, safety evaluations, batch reproducibility studies, and regulatory submissions are necessary. In the nutraceutical sector, the pathway to market is considerably shorter, making this segment a practical starting point for commercial implementation.

Potential impact on the pharmaceutical market

The introduction of carrageenan-based hard-shell capsules could have a significant impact on both the pharmaceutical and nutraceutical sectors in multiple ways:

1. Expansion of plant-based capsule offerings.

Carrageenan-based capsules would expand the portfolio of non-animal capsule materials beyond HPMC, pullu lan, and starch derivatives. Such diversification reduces reliance on animal-derived ingredients, enabling clearer labeling and broader market acceptance.

2. Cost reduction and supply chain stabilization.

Carrageenan production is scalable and cost-effective, potentially lowering the price of plant-based capsules, which currently remain more expensive than gelatin. This economic advantage could incentivize large manufacturers to adopt carrageenan-based alternatives, either to improve profit margins or to reduce consumer prices.

3. Improved access for restricted-diet populations.

Vegan, halal, kosher, and culturally sensitive markets currently depend heavily on HPMC capsules, which are often associated with higher costs. Carrageenan-based capsules could address these needs at a lower cost while offering greater global availability.

4. Compatibility with pH-responsive or targeted drug delivery.

The observed release behavior of HC and HC–MD capsules at elevated pH values supports their potential application in intestinal drug-delivery systems. This property could facilitate future formulation innovations or differentiation in controlled-release dosage forms.

5. Sustainability-driven adoption.

As industries increasingly adopt environmentally conscious materials, carrageenan-based capsules derived from renewable marine biomass could contribute to sustainable pharmaceutical packaging and dosage-form design.

Overall, the introduction of carrageenan-based capsules could transform segments of the capsule market by providing a plant-based, cost-effective, and functionally competitive alternative to gelatin and HPMC, particularly in nutraceutical and OTC applications. With further safety validation and process optimization, carrageenan capsules hold considerable potential for wider adoption in pharmaceutical formulations.

Conclusion

The weight variation test demonstrated that all three capsule types – gelatin, HC, and HC–MD – prepared as erythromycin hard-shell capsules complied with USP weight variation standards. Mechanical strength testing indicated that HC–MD capsules exhibited the highest elastic stiffness, tensile force, and elongation at break, followed by HC and gelatin capsules. Swelling studies revealed that gelatin capsules had a significantly lower swelling index than HC and HC–MD, while disintegration testing showed that HC capsules disintegrated more rapidly than gelatin and HC–MD, suggesting a faster release potential. Erythromycin release was strongly influenced by pH: at pH 1.2, gelatin capsules released the drug more slowly

than HC and HC–MD, whereas at pH 4.5 and 6.8, HC and HC–MD capsules released higher amounts of erythromycin, supporting their suitability for pH-sensitive intestinal drug delivery. Contact angle analysis further suggested that HC and HC–MD formulations possess greater surface wettability, which may enhance drug release in aqueous environments.

Kinetic modeling indicated that erythromycin release across all formulations aligned most closely with zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Hixson–Crowell models. Interpretation of these models, together with swelling and disintegration data, suggests that erythromycin release is primarily governed by matrix diffusion and surface-area effects. The Korsmeyer–Peppas model did not provide an adequate fit and was excluded from mechanistic analysis. Although model selection was based on R^2 values alone, more robust statistical validation is warranted in future studies.

Specifically, zero-order kinetics describes concentration-independent release at a constant rate, whereas first-order kinetics indicates a decreasing release rate as drug content declines. The Higuchi model reflects diffusion-controlled release through the capsule matrix, and the Hixson–Crowell model highlights surface-area-mediated release due to particle size reduction. These findings support the hypothesis that HC and HC–MD matrices provide favorable conditions for controlled erythromycin delivery, particularly under intestinal pH conditions.

Despite these promising results, several limitations should be acknowledged. Mechanical testing was performed under uniaxial compression only, and no in vitro digestion simulations or environmental stability studies were conducted. Consequently, claims regarding oral delivery suitability remain preliminary. Future studies will include enzymatic degradation assays, gastrointestinal simulation, and structural analyses to validate the robustness and biopharmaceutical relevance of HC-based formulations.

Overall, this study contributes to early-stage formulation development by demonstrating that hydrolyzed carrageenan and its maltodextrin blends may serve as functional, plant-based alternatives to gelatin in hard-shell capsule systems.

Acknowledgments

The authors also thank the Presidents' Forum of Southeast and South Asian and Taiwanese Universities (SATU) for facilitating the research collaboration.

References

Adepu S, Ramakrishna S (2021) Controlled drug delivery systems: Current status and future directions. *Molecules* 26: e5905. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26195905>

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

The authors gratefully acknowledge Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia, for funding this research under SK Rektor No. 1003/UN3/2022 through the SATU Joint Research Scheme.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: PP, RTW; Data curation: MRDF, RH; Formal analysis: MRDF, SMM; funding acquisition: PP, RTW; Investigation: MRDF, TS, SMM; Project administration: SH; Resources: PP Software: MRDF; Validation: SW, EH; Visualization: MRDF, TS; Writing original draft: MRDF; Writing-review & editing: PP, RTW.

Author ORCIDs

Muhammad Al Rizqi Dharma Fauzi <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2325-0267>

Pratiwi Pudjiastuti <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0346-3153>

Tri Susanti <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7839-401X>

Syahnur Haqiqoh <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8569-4631>

Siti Wafiroh <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8117-471X>

Esti Hendradi <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8216-8549>

Saeid Mezail Mawazi <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2871-7276>

Riki Haryanto <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-9380-8425>

Riyanto Teguh Widodo <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7087-2873>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

Aliyu RS, Lawal AM, Sharma GK (2020) Evaluation of gelatin-based hard capsules for pharmaceutical applications. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences* 6(8): 93–104.

- Biyani M (2021) HPMC capsules for moisture sensitive and hygroscopic products. *Pharmaceutical Science and Technology* 5(2): 50–52. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.pst.20210502.14>
- Damodharan N (2020) Mathematical modelling of dissolution kinetics in dosage forms. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology* 13(3): 1339–1345. <https://doi.org/10.5958/0974-360X.2020.00247.4>
- Fauzi MARD, Pudjiastuti P, Hendradi E, Widodo RT, Amin M, Mohd CI (2020) Characterization, disintegration, and dissolution analyses of carrageenan-based hard-shell capsules cross-linked with maltodextrin as a potential alternative drug delivery system. *International Journal of Polymer Science*: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/3565931>
- Fauzi MARD, Pudjiastuti P, Wibowo AC, Hendradi E (2021) Preparation, properties and potential of carrageenan-based hard capsules for replacing gelatin: A review. *Polymers* 13(16): 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13162666>
- Hamdan MA, Lakashmi SS, Amin KNM, Adam F (2020) Carrageenan-based hard capsule properties at different drying times. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 736: e052005. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/736/5/052005>
- He C, Yang Y, Zhang M, Zhou K, Huang Y, Zhang N, Ye J, Arowo M, Zheng B, Zhang X, Xu H, Xiao M (2023) Drying process of HPMC-based hard capsules: Visual experiment and mathematical modeling. *Gels* 9(6): e463. <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels9060463>
- He H, Ye J, Zhang X, Huang Y, Li X, Xiao M (2017) κ -Carrageenan/locust bean gum as hard capsule gelling agents. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 175: 417–424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2017.05.082>
- Hilloulin B, Van Tittelboom K, Gruyaert E, De Belie N, Loukili A (2015) Design of polymeric capsules for self-healing concrete. *Cement and Concrete Composites* 55: 298–307. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2014.09.022>
- Huanbutta K, Sangnim T (2019) Design and development of zero-order drug release gastroretentive floating tablets fabricated by 3D printing technology. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science & Technology* 52: 831–837. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2019.06.004>
- Jambhekar SS, Breen PJ (2009) *Basic Pharmacokinetics* (Vol. 7). Pharmaceutical Press, London.
- Liu F, Ranmal S, Batchelor HK, Orlu-Gul M, Ernest TB, Thomas IW, Flanagan T, Tuleu C (2014) Patient-centered pharmaceutical design to improve acceptability of medicines: similarities and differences in paediatric and geriatric populations. *Drugs* 74: 1871–1889. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40265-014-0297-2>
- Majee SB, Avlani D, Biswas GR (2017) HPMC as capsule shell material: physicochemical, pharmaceutical and biopharmaceutical properties. *International Journal of Pharmacy & Pharmaceutical Sciences* 9(10): 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.22159/ijpps.2017v9i10.20707>
- Mawazi SM, Al-Mahmood SMA, Chatterjee B, Hadi HAB, Doolaanea AA (2019) Carbamazepine gel formulation as a sustained release epilepsy medication for pediatric use. *Pharmaceutics* 11(10): 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics11100488>
- Mawazi SM, Doolaanea AA, Hadi HA, Chatterjee B (2021) The impact of carbamazepine crystallinity on carbamazepine-loaded microparticle formulations. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 587: e120638. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2021.120638>
- Mawazi SM, Hadi HAB, Al-Mahmood SMA, Doolaanea AA (2019) Development and validation of UV-Vis spectroscopic method of assay of carbamazepine in microparticles. *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics* 11(1): 34–37. <https://doi.org/10.22159/ijap.2019v11i1.26256>
- Mustafa A, Tomescu A, Mustafa E, Cherim M, Sirbu R (2016) Polyelectrolyte complexes based on chitosan and natural polymers. *European Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies* 4: 100–108.
- Paarakh MP, Jose PA, Setty CM, Christopher GP (2018) Release kinetics – concepts and applications. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research & Technology* 8(1): 12–20. <https://doi.org/10.31838/ijprt/08.01.02>
- Pudjiastuti P, Wafiroh S, Hendradi E, Darmokoesoemo H, Harsini M, Fauzi MARD, Nahar L, Sarker S (2020) Disintegration, in vitro dissolution, and drug release kinetics profiles of κ -carrageenan-based nutraceutical hard-shell capsules containing salicylamide. *Open Chemistry* 18(1): 226–231. <https://doi.org/10.1515/chem-2020-0028>
- Radhakrishnan C, Forough AS, Cichero JAY, Smyth HE, Raidhan A, Nissen LM, Dooley M, Steadman KJ (2021) A difficult pill to swallow: An investigation of the factors associated with medication swallowing difficulties. *Patient Preference and Adherence* 15: 29–40. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S277238>
- Rehman Q, Akash MSH, Rasool MF, Rehman K (2020) Role of kinetic models in drug stability. *Drug Stability & Chemical Kinetics* 155: 155–165. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-6426-0_11
- Ridgway K (1987) *Hard Capsules: Development and Technology*. Pharmaceutical Press, London.
- Samatra MY, Noor NQIM, Razali UHM, Bakar J, Shaarani Smd (2022) Bovidae-based gelatin: extractions method, physicochemical and functional properties, applications, and future trends. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety* 21(4): 3153–3176. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12967>
- Sharma K, Porat Z, Gedanken A (2021) Designing natural polymer-based capsules and spheres for biomedical applications – A review. *Polymers* 13: e4307. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13244307>
- Srividya B, Sowmya C, Reddy CSP (2014) Capsules and its technology: an overview. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics & Drug Analysis* 2(9): 727–733.
- Wójcik-Pastuszka D, Krzak J, Macikowski B, Berkowski R, Osiński B, Musiał W (2019) Evaluation of the release kinetics of a pharmacologically active substance from model intra-articular implants replacing the cruciate ligaments of the knee. *Materials* 12(8): e1202. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12081202>
- Xiao X (2008) Dynamic tensile testing of plastic materials. *Polymer Testing* 27(2): 164–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2007.09.010>
- Yang N, Chen H, Jin Z, Hou J, Zhang Y, Han H, Shen Y, Guo S (2020) Moisture sorption and desorption properties of gelatin, HPMC and pullulan hard capsules. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 159: 659–666. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2020.05.110>
- Zhang L, Wang Y, Liu H, Yu L, Liu X, Chen L, Zhang N, Zhang Z (2013) Developing hydroxypropyl methylcellulose/hydroxypropyl starch blends for use as capsule materials. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 98: 73–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2013.05.070>